

PRECISE TIMING AS A SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

The existence of precise timing as a system is a little recognized but important factor in the new military systems. The new modes of intra-system, inter-system and inter-platform operation require not only a common reference but also survivable means of acquiring and maintaining precise time. Accuracy and survivability of timing is a unique issue involving the common reference, the dissemination systems, and on-board timekeeping. Recent progress, some discussion of the issues, and potential solutions are given.

INTRODUCTION

A growing number of military systems use precise timing to coordinate their operating units. Coordination within a system requires only that the participating units agree precisely within a common, even arbitrary, time scale; it does not inherently require accuracy. However, the idea must be expanded for two major classes of military systems: those which cannot internally support their own time-coordination requirements and those which must interoperate with others. Where many systems must interoperate or use the same timing services, the common time scale must be a widely accepted, designated reference. Then, accuracy, rather than simple precision, better describes the requirement. The reference and the means to disseminate it may themselves be considered a system.

THE NEED FOR PRECISE TIMING

Precise timing is required for many purposes. Some systems need only a precise frequency or rate. Large communications systems such as the Defense Communication System (DCS) with continuous mission bit streams can be stabilized so that traffic flows smoothly, and storage buffers do not overflow or underflow. Bit or frame synchronization tracking loops aided by accurate frequency standards can recover from fades or other continuity gaps without extended synchronization searches. For high bit rate systems, frequency agreement to one part in 10E11 or better may be needed among nodes. To meet these needs, some communications systems have maintained their own system time references and disseminated them through the system. However, traceability to a superior frequency reference at each node

through an external dissemination system can be advantageous for system stability and efficiency, and for interoperation with other systems.

A growing number of other systems require precise time at multiple locations in the form of time of day or date. Communications systems that may depend upon precise time include those that employ such techniques as frequency-hopping or pseudo-random noise; time-division-multiple-access; burst transmissions; pulse-position-modulation; or coherent detection. Also dependent upon precise time are intelligence and navigation systems using time-of-arrival measurements of signals at or from multiple locations, and some identification-friend-or-foe (IFF) systems. However, time coordination or synchronization may be required before the system can be activated, and an external timing system is needed. With coordination through an external time system, units or forces meeting for the first time can communicate and interoperate immediately in an anti-jam or, perhaps, covert mode without vulnerable and inefficient synchronizing transmissions.

In general, it is more difficult to support precise (unambiguous) time requirements than it is to provide only an accurate rate or frequency. Dissemination systems capable of giving unambiguous time can also support frequency dissemination requirements within their accuracies, but the reverse is not necessarily true. The problems of local timekeeping are also generally more difficult than locally maintaining an accurate frequency. (An accurate frequency can be established without an external system by using inherently accurate local references, such as cesium-beam standards). Much of the discussion here addresses the more difficult problem of establishing and maintaining precise time.

MILITARY TIMING SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

There is, in fact, a system to support military precise timing, although it is usually seen more as an assemblage of services than as a designated system. Its reference is Universal Coordinated Time (UTC) maintained by the U.S. Naval Observatory (USNO) Master Clock, which is the designated Department of Defense (DoD) Master Clock. The system (Figure 1) utilizes a number of participating dissemination systems to provide accurate, worldwide traceability to the USNO Master Clock, while designated Precise Time

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FIGURE 1.
PRESENT TIMING SYSTEM

The U.S. Naval Observatory (USNO) monitors and controls timing broadcasts by satellite and terrestrial navigation and other systems that can provide timing to the users. Precise Time Stations aid in the monitoring.

Stations cooperate in the necessary monitoring of the dissemination systems. The dissemination components are largely assets of other systems whose primary mission is to provide some other service, such as navigation or communications. The dissemination function is typically formalized through memoranda of agreement or understanding by which USNO steers system time to within small tolerances; finer corrections may be broadcast through the system or published later. Dissemination services are listed in Time Service Bulletins published by the Observatory.

For military purposes, a timing system has special requirements. It should be worldwide, accurate, reliable, passive (not requiring the user to emit a signal), and survivable through a number of potential threats. Elements of importance (Figure 2) are (1) a common time reference, (2) means of disseminating the reference to the user platforms or systems, (3) the local platform or user-system clocks, and (4) whatever interfaces are needed between elements to make them function together.

Attainment of the military goals is affected by both the design of the elements and the system management practices. Reliability and survivability have special meanings in a timing system. Since time is perishable, survival may depend upon the reliability and timekeeping ability of clocks that maintain time within the system. A user system, for example, that was made to be continuously dependent upon reception of timing signals, would be immediately vulnerable to

FIGURE 2.
ELEMENTS OF A TIMING SYSTEM

loss or degradation of reception. The risk is reduced substantially by giving each level of the hierarchy an independent (autonomous) operating capability. With clocks capable of protracted autonomous operation at each level (reference, dissemination and local), the user may withstand a prolonged loss of service from any higher level. In a timing system designed for maximum survivability, the primary effect of dissemination service loss would be a gradual degradation of accuracy for which the user system should make allowances.

Since the timing system becomes a part of any user system, the timing system should be examined in some detail to assess requirements for local timekeeping, dissemination access, and system management practices. The local clocks are ordinarily needed to avoid continuous dependence upon the dissemination systems and to filter out short-term noise that usually accompanies the dissemination process. In usual operating practice, the clocks are initially set on time through a dissemination service; they may then continue to be regularly updated and, perhaps, rated via the service to track the common reference. They operate autonomously between updates. Where prolonged autonomous operation is expected (in submarine-based systems, for example, or in systems whose link to the common reference might be lost for a protracted period) atomic clocks may be employed.

CLOCKS FOR LOCAL TIMEKEEPING

Of the currently available clocks, those using cesium-beam resonators are usually selected for long-term timekeeping because of their inherent accuracy and absence of a systematic frequency drift with time. Although a clock with a constant drift rate (which produces a timing error that is proportional to the square of elapsed time) might be measured over a period of time and compensated in some applications, uncertainties or changes in the drift rate can cause uncertainties in long-term timekeeping.

Other types of clocks have advantages for specific applications. Improvements in hydrogen maser technology offer promise of clocks with exceptionally good long-term stability (better than a part in 10^{14}) and considerably better timekeeping ability than the current cesium standards in applications where the frequency offset (if any) can be determined before autonomous operation is required. The higher performance models of rubidium cell clocks drift about one part in 10^{11} per month, while the better quartz oscillators drift that amount per day. Performance of quartz oscillators at fixed sites may be improved by continuously monitoring them for an extended period through a dissemination system, e.g., LORAN-C, and correcting for their long-term frequency drift; disadvantages for high-precision, extended-autonomy applications are that oscillator drift rates typically change for an extended period after turn-on, and their drift rates are larger and less predictable than those of rubidium

oscillators. The same method applied to rubidium oscillators, whose drift rates are much smaller and less variable, might provide very acceptable local timekeeping for many purposes.

DISSEMINATION ACCESS REQUIREMENTS

Most of the previous discussion has presumed that a dissemination system would be available to set the local clock on time initially and, if necessary, rate it. Usually, redundant dissemination services would be available. But if clock setting must be accomplished on demand or if the clock is continuously dependent upon the dissemination system, the local timing is no more reliable or survivable than the dissemination system itself, including the timing receiver. If rating is also required soon after the initial clock setting, the dissemination system's precision is a possible limiting factor. Measuring a rate to a resolution of one part in 10^{11} , for example, requires a pair of time difference measurements, each to a precision of ± 432 nanoseconds over a one-day period, or ± 18 nanoseconds for 1 hour. Another limitation for some mobile systems using quartz crystal clocks is the period of large, variable frequency drift after turn-on that makes rating difficult.

To get around some of these limitations for mobile platforms, e.g., aircraft, whose missions are relatively short, a continuously operated reference clock may be maintained at a dispatch point to update the mobile clocks immediately before a mission. While this obviates the necessity for prompt dissemination service, it does not solve a turn-on drift problem. Better performance, if needed, may be realized with continuously operated mobile clocks; when platform power is turned off, they may be maintained in continuous operation from another power source and perhaps even regularly updated until the next mission. The Services are actively seeking ways to improve stability following turn-on and during environmental stresses. They are also developing methods to reduce the power drain of mobile clocks in order to maintain continuous operation and avoid the necessity for prompt service from a dissemination system.

LOCAL CLOCKS AS PART OF THE SYSTEM

Since the timing system is a part of numerous user systems, considerations of economy might suggest pooling resources and extending the system to the local clock level. If the timing system included a clock system on each platform or station, precise time could be tapped by user systems as they would tap the electrical power. This would relieve the user systems of much of their timekeeping burden, and new systems could be made smaller and less expensive.

Aside from the economic aspects, there are operational implications. A properly designed platform system employing a few local clocks could be made more reliable and survivable than any individual clock. ("Properly designed" would include avoidance of creating centralized

vulnerabilities). Some platform-level facilities of this sort have been made for specific platforms or stations. These are individual initiatives, though, and the timing system itself is not functionally responsible at this level, except by specific agreement, as with GPS and SATCOM. But while there is no overall program to extend the DoD timing system to the wall-plug level, some recent developments will help to achieve some of the desired results.

THE SYSTEM OUTLOOK

A new military standard on timing and synchronization for strategic and tactical military communications, MIL-STD-188-115 has been published. It requires systems to use timing traceable to the USNO Master Clock if they might at some time have to interoperate with others. Furthermore, it specifies a standard signal format for comparing local clocks or clock systems of time-dependent networks. With a common time scale and a standard interface, collocated communications nodes will now be able to employ many common resources, although such integration is not mandated by the standard. A superior clock of one communications system, for example, could serve as a local reference or backup for other collocated systems. Communications systems with an inherent time-dissemination or timekeeping capability may easily interface with and serve others.

The Navstar (Global Positioning System (GPS) user equipment (receiver) being developed for tri-service use has adopted an interface that is compatible with the new MIL-STD-188-115. The user equipment provides a 1-pulse-per-second (1-PPS) signal that is accurate with respect to Universal Coordinated Time (UTC) maintained by the USNO Master Clock to within less than 100 nanoseconds (ns). It also provides a time code giving UTC(USNO) time of day, day of year, and a figure of merit in a format compatible with MIL-STD-188-115; it will also accept the time code and 1-PPS from a clock and display the clock error with respect to UTC(USNO). It is expected that other time-dissemination receivers would adopt a compatible interface; most would already work with clocks having the MIL-STD-188-115 interface, even though they might not make full use of it.

GPS, a satellite-based system, is destined to become the primary time-dissemination service for many systems. When it becomes operational in a few years, it will provide continuous, worldwide time dissemination and navigation services for military and civil users. (An accurate position is also needed by some precisely timed systems). The military user equipment is a combination navigation and precise time unit, which will give a three-dimensional position fix to about 50-foot accuracy and time accurate to about 100 ns or better with simultaneous reception from four of the eighteen satellites. At fixed locations, single-channel commercial GPS timing receivers available from several vendors can already provide the UTC(USNO) reference to an accuracy of about 100ns or better when any of the five currently

active developmental satellites is in view.

The USNO Master Clock ensemble, which already carries the highest weighting in the international atomic time scale, is being upgraded through the addition of hydrogen maser clocks and even a newly developed stored mercury ion standard. USNO also maintains good timekeeping facilities at the entry points of certain dissemination systems such as SATCOM and GPS, and plans to add similar facilities at others. Most of the clocks employed in these second-level facilities are high-performance commercial cesium beam standards. They are regularly compared with the USNO Master Clock and can autonomously maintain time accurately (or at least known in terms of the reference) to the order of a microsecond over a period of six months. Hydrogen maser clocks now under development through the GPS Program for military ground and space use are more stable than the current cesium-beam clocks and could give, perhaps, an order of magnitude improvement in timekeeping. An ensemble of these will be installed at the GPS Master Control Station.

Subsequent levels in the major dissemination systems also employ cesium clocks or clock systems that can maintain time autonomously for extended periods. In GPS, for example, the cesium clocks being developed for the spacecraft have specified rate (or frequency) stabilities of one part in 10^{13} at one day. There is reason to believe that they could maintain a similar stability for much longer periods of time and could maintain time to within about 10 nanoseconds per day (1 us for 100 days). The long-term performance of LORAN-C clocks should be similar. While clock performance is not the only factor in long-term timekeeping, (in GPS, the long-term system performance is intimately linked with orbit predictability) the potential for long-term, autonomous timing at the lowest levels of most dissemination systems appears to be very good.

OUTLOOK SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The timing system as it now exists can support stringent timing requirements. Using the developmental GPS satellites and commercially available receivers, time can be established worldwide at fixed sites to within 100-ns accuracy. Coverage will become continuous and better capable of serving mobile users in a few years.

The timing system in its present form, but especially after the full-scale deployment of GPS, will be very reliable, due to its redundancy of assets and built-in survivability provisions. Additional improvements are both possible and relatively easy to implement in the interest of autonomy at the lower dissemination levels. However, much can be done by the user to assure survivability: operating modes can be chosen to avoid requiring prompt service from the dissemination system. An array of better clocks having better stability, smaller size, and lower power drain for on-board timekeeping now being developed will support those operating practices.

The adoption of MIL-STD-188-115 has more securely established military precise timing as a system and has paved the way for its efficient use. As use increases, further economies and more robust and accurate timing should evolve naturally.